

Hierarchical Self-assembly of Peptides and its Applications in Bionanotechnology

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Abstract: Self-assembled structures obtained from organic molecules have shown great potential for applications in a wide range of domains. In this context, short peptides proved to be a particularly versatile class of organic building blocks for self-assembled materials. These species afford the biocompatibility and polymorphic richness typical of proteins while allowing synthetic availability and robustness typical of smaller molecules. At the nano-to-mesoscale, the architectures obtained from peptide units exhibit stability and a large variety of morphologies, the most common of which are nanotubes, nanoribbons and nanowires. In this review, we describe the formation of peptide-based self-assembled structures triggered by different stimuli (*e.g.*, ionic strength, pH, and polarity), and the interactions that drive the assembling processes. We will survey how judicious molecular design has been exploited to impart favourable assembling properties to afford systems with desired characteristics. A large body of literature provides the experimental and *in silico* data to predict self-assembly in a given peptide system and obtain different supramolecular organizations for applications in a wide range of fields, from transport to sensing, from catalysis to drug delivery and tissue regeneration.

Keywords: Peptide assemblies, hybrid peptides, cross- β structure, biosensor, supramolecular chemistry, molecular and cellular biology.

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1. Self-assembling peptides: a brief historical perspective

The phenomenon of self-assembly in biological systems is fundamental for the formation of supramolecular structures such as DNA, proteins and lipid membranes, which perform fundamental functions in biological processes underpinning the storage and transfer of information (DNA and RNA), the spatial delimitation of compartments (membranes) and catalysis and communication (proteins) among others.^[1]

The discovery of the first peptide system capable of self-assembly took place in the late 80s when a putative DNA-binding protein, later named zuotin, was isolated from the type 1 fimbriae of *Escherichia coli*; this protein, involved in mediating the attachment of the microorganism to eukaryotic cells,^[2] was known to assemble into a right-handed helix and crucially to recover its ability to reassemble following denaturation. A repeat of 16-residue peptides was later identified as the responsible for the intriguing self-assembling behaviour of the protein. The repeats were characterised by alanine residues alternated with positively and

negatively charged amino acids (*e.g.*, the EAK16-II peptide sequence AEAEAKAKAEAEAKAK). Synthetically obtained peptides were able to self-assemble into unusually stable β -sheet structures and into nanofibrous scaffolds. This observation initiated the discovery of numerous self-assembling sequences designed to obtain bottom-up soft materials.^[3-5] Further capital advancement in this field were fuelled by the identification of short sequences responsible of the self-assembly of the amyloid- β (A β) peptide, associated with Alzheimer's disease.^[6] Since the emergence of the pentapeptide KLVFF and the dipeptide FF as self-assembling building blocks, a variety of low-molecular weight organic gelators (LMWOGs) based on peptides were designed to obtain nanostructures with favourable physical and mechanical features for application in different fields.

The first report on nanostructures built from amino acid units was in the early 1990's. In the study reported in reference [7] the antiparallel stacking of *cyclo*[-D-Ala-Glu-D-Gln]₂- sequences was used to form open-ended tubular assemblies. Peptide building blocks are biocompatible, chemically versatile, and provide a facile route towards a scale-up synthesis process.^[8-12] Along with the synthesis and growth of peptide nanostructures in various geometries and morphology, integration of peptides with metal-organic framework and functionalization with metal nanoparticles have been demonstrated.

Reches and Gazit were the pioneers on the study of hydrophobic diphenylalanine (FF) self-assembly for mimicking amyloid-like nanostructures, forming rigid nanotubes.^[13] In addition, they found that FF self-assemblies serve as excellent sacrificial templates for fabrication of Ag nanowires through a reductive process.^[13] Furthermore, a morphological transition was observed when phenylglycine (Phg) was used as the dipeptide motif.^[14] Phg offers constrained rotational freedom around the C-C bond, which helps in the formation of very stable Phg-Phg dipeptide nanoscale vesicles. A similar morphological switch was also observed when FF dipeptide was conjugated to a cysteine residue.^[15] This tri-peptide self-assembled into soft nanospheres suggesting that the disulfide bridge formation results in the closure of nanotubes.

The polymorphism of FF-based nanostructures can be controlled by the experimental incubation conditions such as solvent, peptide concentration, pH and temperature.^[16] For example, triphenylalanine peptides (FFF) self-assemble into nanospheres or nanorods, which are different from the nanovesicles and nanotubes formed by diphenylalanine (FF) peptides by simply tuning the FF peptide concentration.^[17]

The development of bioinspired systems is a cutting-edge research area for environmentally-safe and sustainable materials. The potential applications of these nanostructures have been demonstrated in the design of optical waveguides,^[18,19]

neurotransmitter and enzymatic sensing,^[20-25] rational drug design,^[26,27] photodynamic therapy,^[28-31] solar cells,^[32] and optical biosensors.^[33] Among the various biological molecular assemblies available, peptide nanostructures can be easily modified with biomolecules, transition metals, conjugated polymers, and magnetic materials enhancing their functionality for applications in nanotechnology.

2. Design-nanostructure relationships in self-assembling peptides

In this section, we will discuss how the molecular structure of the peptide affects the morphology of the nanostructure formed since the combination of different amino acids (see section 1) produces peptides/proteins with different physicochemical properties,^[34] and morphology, where each type of morphology could be applied in a specific knowledge area.^[35]

Although the mechanisms underpinning self-assembly are not completely elucidated, some of the driving forces responsible for the establishment of intermolecular interactions have been well characterised. From the very early studies on self-assembling peptides it emerged that electrostatic interactions, hydrogen bonds and hydrophobic effects were pivotal triggers for the association of the peptide chains in solution leading to the formation of larger aggregates and nanoscale assemblies.

The self-assembly of natural and non-natural amino acids in peptides and proteins is a result of the balance of weak non-covalent forces,^[36] including electrostatic interactions^[3] and solvophobic effects, hydrogen bonds, van der Waals forces, and π - π stacking (Figure 1).^[34]

Figure 1. Strength of common non-covalent interactions present in peptide self-assembly in aqueous solutions.

Aromatic amino acids (e.g., phenylalanine and tyrosine) and non-polar amino acids (e.g., leucine, alanine and valine) mainly self-assemble through hydrophobic effects and/or π - π stacking, while the self-assembly of polar amino acids occurs predominantly through hydrogen bonding or electrostatic interactions, depending on whether they are uncharged (e.g., serine and asparagine) or charged (e.g., histidine, lysine and glutamic acid).^[36]

The type of interaction among amino acids is the main determinant of the secondary structure adopted by the peptide in solution (e.g., α -helices, β -sheets, extended/random-coil, etc) (Figure 2). For instance, π - π stacking interactions tend to induce the formation of β -sheets, β -turns and α -helix conformations.

Figure 2. Structural classification of peptides. (A) α -helical, (B) β -sheet, (C) extended and (D) loop peptides.

Amphiphilic peptides aggregate to form different structures depending on the triggering stimulus and the experimental conditions, giving rise to nanofibers, nanoribbons, nanobelts, micelles, nanospheres, nanotubes, vesicles, planar membranes, etc.^[36, 37] Numerous approaches have been followed to impart the desired amphiphilic character to peptide sequences: this led to the design of pure linear peptides, ionic-complementary peptides, long-chain alkylated peptides, peptide phospholipids, and peptide-based block copolymers.

A successful strategy to induce and control the self-assembling behaviour of peptides consists in modifying either of the sequence termini with suitable groups.^[36]

In section 1, it was shown that various nanostructures can be formed by self-assembly of different peptide molecular structures (amphiphilic peptides, cyclic peptides, and hybrid peptides).^[35, 38]

2.1. Amphiphilic self-assembling peptides

Amphiphilic peptides are characterised by the presence of hydrophobic and hydrophilic regions in the sequence. Similar to surfactants, lipids and proteins, these species can self-assemble into nanotubes, vesicles and micelles.^[35, 39] The self-assembly is driven by the hydrophobic effect, i.e., the tendency of water or any kind of polar solvent to minimize contact

with the hydrophobic moiety, and it is a widespread and effective way to build self-assembled nanostructures.^[40] The intramolecular distribution of the hydrophobic and hydrophilic portions of the amphiphilic molecule influences the morphology of the peptide nanostructure obtained.^[41] To predict the structure of the assembled aggregate obtained by a given amphiphilic sequence, a parameter called critical packing factor (C_{pp}) has been defined as:

$$C_{pp} = \frac{V_0}{A_{mic} \cdot l_c}$$

where V_0 is the volume occupied by the hydrophobic portion of the chain in the aggregate core, A_{mic} is the area occupied by the polar region and l_c is the maximum chain length. Thus, it has been shown that the aggregate can adopt a spherical (for $C_{pp} \leq 1/3$), a cylindrical (for $1/3 \leq C_{pp} \leq 1/2$), or a lamellar structure (for $C_{pp} = 1$). Vesicles with closed spherical or ellipsoidal structure usually form for $1/2 \leq C_{pp} \leq 1$, as shown in

C_{pp}	Geometry amphiphilic molecule	Structure
$p < \frac{1}{3}$		
$\frac{1}{3} < p < \frac{1}{2}$		
$\frac{1}{2} < p < 1$		
$p > 1$		

Figure 3.^[42]

C_{pp}	Geometry amphiphilic molecule	Structure
$p < \frac{1}{3}$		
$\frac{1}{3} < p < \frac{1}{2}$		
$\frac{1}{2} < p < 1$		
$p > 1$		

Figure 3. Influence of the geometry of the molecule by the variation of the parameter C_{pp} value of packaging in the supramolecular structure.

2.2. Linear peptides and ionic-complementary peptides

Linear peptides are the simplest amphiphilic peptides. In these species sequences of hydrophobic amino acids (G, A, V, L, I and F) alternate with hydrophilic amino acids (D, K, E, R and H).^[43] In linear amphiphilic peptides one-to-three amino acids constitute the hydrophilic region and five or more (up to 8) the hydrophobic region, as for example in linear amphiphilic peptides A_6D , V_6D , G_8DD and KV_6 .^[39] In these species the hydrophobic effect drives the interaction of the molecules to obtain an oligomeric aggregate, which in turn self-assembles to give larger assembled structures of mesoscopic size. Figure 4 shows the proposed assembly pattern of peptide V_6D ,^[39] which is suggested to assemble into vesicles, to then evolve into intermediary structures such as nanotubes and finally into the formation of a network of open-ended nanotubes (*hierarchical self-assembly*).

Figure 4. Potential pathway of V₆D peptide nanotube formation. Reprinted with permission from ^[39] Copyright 2019 American Chemical Society.

Ionic-complementary peptides are formed by an alternating arrangement of negatively and positively charged amino acid residues in the hydrophilic section of the sequence.^[43,44] This arrangement of opposite charges gives the peptides the possibility to interact and aggregate thanks to electrostatic interactions, which contributes, along with hydrogen bonding and Van der Waals forces, to the formation of a β -sheet ordered pattern subsequently allowing the building of nanofibers (Figure 5).^[35,43,45]

The interesting feature of this type of architecture is their structural difference from the linear peptide molecule models: ionic-complementary peptides have charged side chains and a hydrophobic side chain.^[35]

This pattern of assembly has been suggested for self-assembling peptide EAK-16, which forms stable β -sheets in water thanks to interactions between positively charged residues (lysine) and negatively charged residues (glutamate), as shown in *Figure 5*.^[46]

Figure 5. Self-assembling peptides are arranged in stable β -sheets at low pH and low ionic strength. Upon exposure to physiological pH and ionic strength, the peptides form stable nanofibers with a diameter of 10 nm and 50–200 nm pores. Reprinted with permission from [46] Copyright 2019, Elsevier.

2.3. Long-chain alkyl and alkyl peptides

Long-chain alkylated peptides feature a sequence of hydrophilic amino acids and a hydrophobic alkyl chain conjugated on either or both the *N*- or *C*-termini. An example of these species is peptide PA, whose molecular design comprises four elements (*Figure 6-A*): 1) a hydrophobic tail; 2) a β -sheet forming segment; 3) charged groups; and 4) bioactive epitopes.^[47] In aqueous solution, these alkylated peptides cluster to form cylindrical nanofibers (*Figure 6-C*),^[35] which can be used for bone growth since this peptide mimics collagen fibers.^[47] On the other hand, “*multialkyl*” peptides have more than one alkyl chain, and due to their geometry, they lead to the formation of bilayers, which could constitute vesicles or lamellar phases and be applied for interfacial molecular recognition purposes.^[48] As long-chain alkyl and multi-alkyl peptides are different from other types of peptides, the determination of the supramolecular structures they form must take into account steric factors (volume occupied by the alkyl chain) as well as common non-covalent interactions. The nanofibers formed by the PA peptides mimic collagen fibers and were successfully used to support the biomineralization during bone regrowth.

Figure 6. (A) Chemical structure of the peptide amphiphile. (B) Molecular model of the PA. (C) Schematic self-assembly of PA molecules into a cylindrical micelle. Adapted with permission from ^[47] Copyright 2019, The American Association for the Advancement of Science.

2.4. Cyclic peptides

Cyclic peptides with alternated *D*- and *L*-amino acids (Figure 7-A) self-assemble to form nanotube structures composed of a stack of flat cyclic monomers, and the whole structure is stabilized by hydrogen bonds between amide groups in the peptide cycles (Figure 7-B).^[38] These species are highly hydrophobic and are usually soluble only in organic solvents. Compared to amphiphilic peptides, cyclic peptides have two advantages: (a) the nanotube diameter can be controlled by the peptide chain length and side-chain size, and (b) incorporation of suitably functionalised amino acids can impart the desired behaviour to the resulting nanotubes.^[35] Scanlon *et al.* showed that is possible to coat the nanotubes with different polymers, allowing specific tuning of the surface of the nanostructure.^[39]

Figure 7. Schematic diagram of nanotube assembly from cyclic *D,L*-peptides. For clarity, most of the peptide side-chains have been omitted. Reprint with permission from ^[49] Copyright 2019, John Wiley & Sons.

2.5. Hybrid peptide systems

Hybrid peptide systems, either of natural, synthetic or semi-synthetic origin, typically consist of 8-30 amino acid residues. They have the ability to translocate across biological membranes and transport diverse molecular cargoes, either covalently or non-covalently attached, which would otherwise be poorly internalized.

Figure 8. Schematic illustration of the hierarchical organization of a hybrid molecule composed of porphyrin and a polymer. The porphyrin-polymer conjugate self-assembles in nanotubes giving rise to the formation of hydrogel.

In addition, many materials such as, quantum dots, carbon nanotubes, metal oxides, polymers have been modified with peptides for various biological applications.^[50-52] One type of conjugation investigated in recent years is the combination of peptides and polymers. When polymers are bound to peptides, they form hybrid hydrogels with high hydrophobicity and good adhesion to the cell membrane. In the formation of hydrogels, peptides have an essential role for structuring during hydrogelation to achieve consistent mechanical properties. The peptide-polymer conjugates generally show cooperative folding transitions, which enable high biomimetic control of the hydrogel formation at the nanoscale level. In addition to the

peculiarities of the peptides for predictability of the conjugate structure and performance, the characteristics of the polymeric moiety such as chain size and crystallinity are also fundamental.^[53-55]

Synthetic polymers are extremely versatile with respect to their properties, compositions and structures; however, they are unable to naturally bind and recognize peptides and proteins.

3. Design-nanostructure relation to environmental conditions

The self-assembly process does not only depend on intermolecular interactions between peptide chains but is also strongly affected by environmental factors. Variations in temperature, ionic strength, pH, concentration of the substrates and the solvent choice can determine the morphology of the self-assembled peptide nanostructure, as they can alter some of the interaction forces among the peptides and can trigger a change in the structural organization of the peptides.^[35,56] The detailed knowledge about the structure of these systems and its repercussion on the resulting chemical and physical properties is a crucial step for understanding these materials and to design new applications.

Changes in pH and ionic strength of the medium alter the electrostatic interactions between peptide chains and/or between peptide and solvent molecules, whereas modifications of the concentration or change of the solvent usually have an impact on the van der Waals and hydrophobic interactions established between the self-assembling species.^[57]

Stupp *et al.* have proposed a self-assembly strategy to amphiphilic peptides by molecular dynamic simulations, and obtained a “phase diagram” by combining the hydrogen bonding strength and hydrophobic attraction strength (see Figure 9).^[58] They found that “purely” hydrophobic interaction leads to micelle structures, while the “pure” hydrogen bonding interactions results in the aggregation of 2D β -sheets. The final assembly kinetics could show the synergistic effect of these non-covalent interactions.

Figure 9. Schematic phase diagram of AP assemblies.^[58]

The aggregation of these peptide sequences can be followed in different chemical environments - with distinct pHs, ionic strengths, etc. – to determine the critical aggregation concentration (*cac*).^[59] In this case, measurements can be performed by using circular dichroism and fluorescence spectroscopy employing pyrene derivatives, thioflavin T, 8-anilidonaphthalene-1-sulfonic acid or Congo red as fluorescent probes. Spectroscopic methods can also be used to investigate chemical bonds involved in the stabilization and the secondary structure of the complexes. Direct-space visualization can be provided by several microscopy techniques across the mesoscale, including optical (polarising, fluorescence and confocal), electron and atomic force microscopy.^[60]

Variation of the pH of the medium dictates whether the carboxylic and amino groups on the peptide chain are in a protonated or a deprotonated state, which in turn determines the type, strength and geometry of the interaction.^[57] For example, it was demonstrated that peptide EAK-16, which self-assembles into stable β -sheets in water, depending on the pH or electrolyte concentration in the medium produces hydrogel nanofibers.^[46] Chen et al. studied the effect of pH variation on EAK16-type peptides (*Figure 10-A*) capable of hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions as well as electrostatic interactions. As EAK-16, these peptides are composed of glutamic acid and lysine residues with side chain pK_a values of 4.25 and 10.53,

respectively.^[61,62] To test the effect of pH on the formation of self-assembled nanostructures, two extreme pH conditions were used: 1) pH 4, below the pK_a of glutamic acid, and 2) pH 11, above the pK_a of lysine. Therefore, either glutamic acid or lysine was neutralized. The behaviour of the peptide at an intermediate pH value of 6.85 was also examined. For EAK16-IV peptide, AFM images show that the peptide self-assembly changes from a fibrillar to a globular state and returns to a fibrillar state when the pH increased from 4 to 11 (*Figure 10-B*). These studies confirmed that reduction in electrostatic interactions by changing pH does facilitate nanofiber formation in systems containing certain amino acid sequences, which is comparable to what has been observed in other studies.^[61,63]

Figure 10. (A) Schematic three-dimensional molecular model of EAK16-IV (AEAEAEAEAKAKAKAK). (B) AFM images of EAK16-IV upon changing the pH from 4 to 11. Adapted with permission from^[62] Copyright 2019, American Chemical Society.

Nyrkova *et al.* used four similar sequences with eleven amino acid residues, called P₁₁-X, where “X” is the label of the sequence (*Figure 11*). The hierarchical self-assembly of peptide P₁₁-2 had previously been characterised (tapes → ribbon → fibrils → fibers), and the study was later extended to three new peptide sequences at varying pH values.^[64,65]

P₁₁-2: CH₃CO-Gln-Gln-Arg-Phe-Gln-Trp-Gln-Phe-Glu-Gln-Gln-NH₂
P₁₁-3: CH₃CO-Gln-Gln-Arg-Phe-Gln-Trp-Gln-Phe-Gln-Gln-Gln-NH₂
P₁₁-4: CH₃CO-Gln-Gln-Arg-Phe-Glu-Trp-Gln-Phe-Glu-Gln-Gln-NH₂
P₁₁-5: CH₃CO-Gln-Gln-Orn-Phe-Orn-Trp-Orn-Phe-Gln-Gln-Gln-NH₂

Figure 11. *P₁₁ sequences.*

Nanofiber formation was observed for all the sequences studied. Several experimental techniques were used to construct a phase diagram for each peptide as a function of pH (Figure 12). All sequences exhibit a phase change following pH modification, with P₁₁-4 sequence showing the greatest polymorphism among all the species. For this sequence, an isotropic phase of the nanofibers was observed for pH > 7, followed by a nematic fluid phase in the region between pH 5 and 7, then a flocculating phase for pH between 3 and 5 and finally a nematic hydrogel phase for pH values lower than 3. The transmission electron micrographs and optical micrographs showed the difference between the two nematic phases: the nematic fluid phase (5 < pH < 7) exhibits the typical organization of the phase, whereas in the nematic gel, the fibers twist together, while still preserving the order characteristic of the nematic phase (Figure 12).^[66]

Figure 12. (A) Polarized optical micrograph and transmission electron micrograph of P_{11-3} at pH 3. (B) Summary of phase behavior of 11 amino acid peptides in aqueous solution as a function of pH. For P_{11-2} , P_{11-3} , and P_{11-4} , $c=6.3$ mM, and for P_{11-5} , $c=13.1$ mM. (C) Polarized optical micrograph and transmission electron micrograph of P_{11-5} at pH 9. (D) Schematic showing the global arrangement of fibrils in nematic fluids and the fiber-like junctions in nematic gel states. Adapted with permission from ^[66] Copyright 2019, American Chemical Society.

In another work, different types of amphiphilic peptides (PA) feature a palmitoyl chain as the hydrophobic portion of the molecule and six peptide sequences in the hydrophilic part.^[67] For this study, a phase diagram was built which considered the PA concentration as function of pH (Figure 13-C). By increasing the concentration of PA, the formation of cylindrical micelles was observed at low pH values, while spherical micelles were formed under all other conditions, indicating that the pH change promotes a change in the packing factor (see section 2), which is 1/3 for spherical micelles and is between 1/3 and 1/2 for cylindrical micelles. These morphological changes were also observed by TEM, as shown in Figure 11 A-B.

Figure 13. TEM images of PA6 at (A) pH 6.6 and (B) pH 10.0. (C) Concentration-pH phase diagram of PA6 (blue) overlaid on the same for PA5 (pink). Adapted with permission from ^[67] Copyright 2019, American Chemical Society.

Changes in self-organization are also influenced by the temperature of the medium. Previous works observed that above their critical aggregation concentration, PA peptides, specifically C₁₆-KTTKS, form nanotapes composed of bilayers with an inter-layer spacing of 52.5 Å at room temperature.^[68] By increasing the temperature of the system, a phase transition of the nanotapes to the cylindrical micelles was observed (*Figure 14*), which showed a Krafft temperature (i.e., the critical temperature for the transition from soluble micelles to insoluble aggregates) of 30 °C.

Figure 14. A phase diagram for C_{16} -KTTKS constructed from the solubility data from NMR experiments. Adapted with permission ^[68] Copyright 2019, Royal Society of Chemistry.

The temperature can also be used to change the secondary structures, meaning that it affects the hydrogen-bonding and hydrophobic interactions. This occurs because the hydrogen bonds have energy in the order of k_bT , so small fluctuations in temperature can promote the increase/decrease of these bonds (by lowering/raising the temperature). For example, Zang *et al.* ^[69] studied the behavior of peptide polymers (poly-L-glutamates) as a function of temperature. The authors observed a structural transition from α -helical (Figure 15-A) to random coil (Figure 15-B) with increase of temperature, resulting in temperatureresponsive behavior.

Figure 15. Intermolecular hydrogen bonding illustration of (a) helical PP and (b) a random coil PP. Adapted with permission ^[69] Springer Nature and Copyright Clearance Center, 2019.

4. Functional self-assembled peptide nanostructures and their properties

Over the last several years, self-assembled peptides attracted considerable attention as new materials with potential application in research and industry alike. Natural and synthetic peptides with strong self-assembly propensity give the possibility to access a wide range of different nanostructures and the corresponding properties. Numerous applications have been studied including 3D cell culture and tissue regeneration, drug delivery, biosensing, bioimaging, and microbiology and in the elaboration of new materials (Figure 13). In this section of the review, some of those applications will be discussed.

Figure 16. Schematic illustration of peptide nanostructures and possible applications by self-assembly.

4.1. Functional self-assembled peptide nanostructures for drug delivery

One of the key challenges in medicine is the creation of therapeutic agents that exert their effect only in the specific area/tissue where their action is needed.^[70] A large number of drugs benefit from being incorporated in targeting systems/devices: these are the therapeutic agents that are either poorly stable following a given administration pathway or that display toxic effects. For example, orally administered protein and peptides seldom achieve the desired bioavailability because of their lability to the enzymatic arsenal of the gastro-intestinal tract, and because of the scarce ability to cross the intestinal epithelium and the vascular endothelial barriers: in this case the use of a drug delivery system may enhance the stability of the drug or its ability to cross barriers and reach the blood stream. Targeted drug delivery system can help by specifically targeting diseased tissues and cells, thus allowing to decrease the dosage drugs thanks to improved efficacy and minimising the chances of adverse effects against healthy tissue.^[71,72] Amongst the fundamental features of any candidate drug delivery vehicle, the lack of toxicity and the versatility to obtain a drug reservoir based on soft matter are prominent. Self-assembling peptides received considerable interest as starting material to obtain drug delivery systems because of their biocompatibility and because of the possibility they offer of

obtaining an array of structures, from nanomicelles and nanoparticles to injectable hydrogels.^[73]

Self-assembling dipeptide diphenylalanine (FF) has been extensively studied as a starting material to obtain drug delivery systems.^[74-76] Many studies have been carried out to self-assemble FF dipeptides into different nanostructures, including nanoparticles, nanotubes, nanovesicles, and nanowires (see Figure 17).^[77] Microtubes obtained from the self-assembly of FF have been successfully evaluated as drug delivery vehicles for the biological marker rhodamine in an *in vitro* test, which also demonstrated the low toxicity of the dipeptide.^[27]

Figure 17. FF dipeptide structures and applications.

A biomaterial comprising dipeptide FF and konjac glucomannan was used to obtain a rigid hydrogel to incorporate and release hydrophobic drug docetaxel.^[78] The release profile of the drug could be altered by changing the concentration of the hydrogel components and the aging time of the gel. Hydrogel nanoparticles were obtained from Fmoc-FF dipeptide by inverse emulsion using vitamin E-TPGS; they efficiently encapsulated gold nanoparticles and model drugs such as doxorubicin and 5-fluorouracil.^[76]

Self-assembled peptides have also been used for anticancer drug delivery with promising results. Luteinizing hormone-releasing hormone (LHRH) targeted polysaccharide

nanoparticles for tumor-targeted delivery and controlled release of cisplatin (CDDP) have been developed for the targeted treatment of breast cancer.^[79] Cisplatin is one of the most common anticancer agents for treating different kinds of solid tumors today, but similarly to most anticancer drugs, it has severe toxic side effects on healthy tissues and nonspecific biodistribution.^[80] An attempt to simultaneously inhibit the primary tumor growth and organ-specific metastasis by using cisplatin-loaded LHRH-modified dextran nanoparticles (Dex-SA-CDDP-LHRH) was performed, which proved that (LHRH)-targeted nanoparticles markedly enhanced the accumulation of CDDP in the injected primary tumor and metastasis-containing organs while significantly reducing the nephrotoxicity of CDDP (Figure 18).^[81]

Figure 18. Schematic illustration of the chemical composition of Dex-SA-CDDP and Dex-SA-CDDP-LHRH nanoparticles and the illustration of preparing orthotopic mammary tumor metastasis model and the corresponding therapeutic effects of different administrations. Adapted with permission ^[81] Copyright 2019, Elsevier.

4.2. Tissue engineering

Currently, when organs or tissues are critically compromised, transplantation is the most effective surgical procedure; however, it presents many problems, such as low number of potential donors, long waiting lists and the possibility of chronic rejection of the transplanted organ due to incompatibility with the recipient tissue.^[82] A further important shortcoming is the limited number of organs (liver, kidney, pancreas, lung, heart and intestine) and tissues (cornea, bones, bone marrow, valves, muscles, tendons, skin, veins and arteries) that can be transplanted.^[83] Other methods used are surgical reconstructions and the use of implants, both of which are limited by the type and location of the trauma and the possibility of rejection in the case of implants.

In this scenario, a promising alternative is the tissue engineering technique, an interdisciplinary science in which defective organs or tissues can be regenerated from stem cells or autologous tissue samples obtained by biopsy that are later divided into cells. After cell dissociation of the tissue sample, the culture starts on scaffolds, followed by tissue development and implantation in the patient.^[84] The procedure follows the generic steps described below, with some variations dictated by the type of tissue regenerated and by the different standardization bodies:^[85] choice of scaffold; inoculation of the cells in the scaffold; tissue development; surgery for implanting the organ or tissue; and phase of assimilation (see *Figure 19*).

Figure 19. Basic principles of tissue engineering.

Scaffolds are three-dimensional structures that mimic the extracellular matrix and should invariably be constructed with biodegradable materials so that the organism can easily eliminate them after the assimilation phase. Scaffolds also provide support for developing tissues, and they enable feeding of the system with various regulatory molecules, such as nutrients, metabolites and growth factors.^[86]

In the culture process, there are several biomolecules, such as amphiphilic peptides, that can contribute to the growth of the cell population.^[87] These nanomaterials, due to easy interactivity

with plasma membranes,^[88] are organized into a kind of coating for cells during culture, favouring cell proliferation.^[89] An interesting example is the research with the bolaamphiphilic peptide RFL₄FR, the high efficiency of which was verified in culture tests. Cryo-TEM images of RFL₄FR showed self-assembly in thin and homogeneous membranes that are very flexible and have large surface areas, which are fundamental characteristics for coating substrates.^[90] Tests carried out with human stem cell factor (hSCF) varying the concentration of peptide solutions demonstrated that the samples were still as functional as the control after five days, which evidenced that there was no toxicity at these concentrations. With these data, the authors suggested that at 0.1% by weight, RFL₄FR showed promising behaviour which enables its use in future applications as a coating substrate for cell culture.^[90]

The peptides can also directly affect osteogenic processes by interfering with the growth and crystallinity of hydroxyapatite (crystalline calcium phosphate, HA, Ca₁₀(OH)₂(PO₄)₆), a natural inorganic constituent of bone and teeth. In a study conducted by Roy and co-workers, a peptide sequence (SVSVG₄MKPSRP) capable of strongly binding to phosphate, which is abundant in HA, was identified by the phage display process.^[91] In addition, fluorescence microscopy has demonstrated that adhesion does not occur in amorphous calcium phosphate (Ca₃(PO₄)₂), thus attesting to the peptide specificity, both chemically and structurally, which is equivalent to the polymorphic variety present in the body.^[91] This selectivity is promising for future studies of osteogenic monitoring and differentiation of stem cells.

4.3. Polypeptides for 3D tissue cultures

Cell culture in two dimensions has been routinely and diligently undertaken in thousands of laboratories worldwide for the past four decades. However, the culture of cells in two dimensions is arguably primitive and does not reproduce the anatomy or physiology of a tissue for informative or useful study.^[92,93] For this reason, current research in this area is focused on the development of materials for the preparation of cell cultures in three dimensions; these models exhibit features that are closer to the complex *in vivo* conditions, mimicking cell growth in natural conditions.^[94] For this type of cultures, polymers such as peptides and proteins have been developed due to the promising properties.

A highly promising self-assembling protein used for developing 3D culture scaffolds is fibroin, obtained from different kinds of silk. Fibroins have the following traits: excellent biocompatibility *in vivo*; optimized physical properties, especially mechanical properties; the ability for the construction of topographic and morphological cues; degradability with safe by-products; and diffusivity control.^[95,96] Silk fibroin (SF) can be arranged to hold a broad range

of forms, such as solutions, powders, fibers, films, hydrogels, and sponges;^[97] this allows the use of SF for constructing structures on many different scales, ranging across the nano-, micro-, and macroscales, with unique biological functions (Figure 17).^[98] Silk fibroin has been widely used in the elaboration of scaffolds for regeneration of bone and skin tissue.^[97] Garcia-Fuentes *et al.* prepared scaffolds with porous microstructures by freeze-drying aqueous solutions of silk fibroin and hyaluronan and subsequently incubating the solutions in methanol to induce water insolubility of silk fibroin; histology of the constructs after cell culture showed enhanced cellular growth into silk fibroin/hyaluronan scaffolds compared to that of plain silk fibroin scaffolds. Silk fibroin scaffolds have also been tested as an alternative approach for repairing severe bone injuries. Mamatha *et al.* proved that fibroin polyvinyl alcohol prepared by freeze-drying methods are efficient, nontoxic and supportive to osteoblast-like cells. In addition to silk fibroin, other peptides have been used, such as elastin-like polypeptides (ELPS), inclusion bodies (IBS) formed from recombinant proteins, short peptides with β -sheet and α -helical secondary structures and short peptides with aromatic residues.^[99] Elastin is an extracellular insoluble matrix protein found in connective tissues, and it is synthesized from soluble tropoelastin monomers, which become extensively crosslinked in the extracellular matrix and form large complex arrays.^[100] Compared with scaffolds without elastin, scaffolds coated with elastin have presented a high interaction between tropoelastin monomers and fibroblast cells, showing that tropoelastin, a precursor of elastin, promotes fibroblast adhesion, proliferation, and spreading.^[101]

Figure 20. *Silk Fibroin scaffold for 3D Cell Culture.*

4.4. Biosensors and electronic devices

Biosensors are analytical devices that convert biological responses into quantifiable signals; they are composed of a transducer that converts the chemical interaction into electrical response

and an interface architecture that holds the bioreceptor, which binds specifically to the selected analyte.^[102,103] Many types of biorecognition can be used to this end, such as enzymes, antibodies, antigens, aptamers, and lectins.^[102] For example, in the Figure 21 the author developed an electrochemical genosensor for detection of breast cancer marker BRCA.^[104]

Figure 21. Fabrication process of a peptide-based electrochemical sensor for breast cancer. Adapted with permission from ^[104] Copyright 2019, Elsevier.

However, these biomolecules can be easily degraded by enzymes and therefore lose their functionality; their synthesis can also be costly and complex.

As previously described, the primary structure will contribute to define, together with the environmental conditions, the protein secondary and tertiary structure, which provide high organization and performance of biological activities with high specificity. In this context, peptides can be selected as bioreceptors in antibody-antigen interactions,^[25] which is mainly due to its synthetic approach; this enables the synthesis only of the recognized sequence (epitope), simulating the molecular interaction that occurs in the immune system.^[105] Other types of biorecognition are available for further detection, such as the use of peptides as enzymatic substrates as a way to detect enzymatic activity and the use of specific peptides for DNA/RNA sensing, protein sensing and metallic ion sensing.^[102]

Peptides can also work as an interface architecture for other bioreceptors. Matsui et al. shows several types of architectures of biosensors based on functionalized peptide nanotubes (Figure 22-A), allowing the detection of viruses and heavy metallic ions and their use as probes for bacteria and other microorganism sensing.^[106] The authors showed that after the modification of peptide nanotubes with biologically active molecules, it is possible to target and bind specific molecules, like antibody, metals or a cell receptor (Figure 22-C). Suitable

physicochemical perturbation of the medium allowed then to separate the bound peptide nanotube and submit it to analysis, correlating it to the analytic concentration (Figure 22-E).

Figure 22. A) Representation of nanotube self-assembled from bolaamphiphile peptides; B) TEM image of nanotube (scale bar=100 nm); C) bacteria agglutinated by the interaction with antibodies on peptide nanotubes sediment fast, and the increased number of the insulating cells on the transducer via the sedimentation increases the impedance at 316 kHz; D) control nanotubes modified with rabbit IgG that do not interact specifically with *E. coli*, and do not sediment these cells fast enough to generate the impedance signal; E) Multiplexed detection of pathogens with the peptide nanotube biochip; variations of the real part of the impedance (Z') of samples containing *E. coli* and *S. typhi* in various concentrations, was converted into a colour chart. Adapted with permission from ^[106] Copyright 2019, John Wiley and Sons.

Other approaches use peptides as thin films for further functionalization for biosensing means,^[8] as well as thin films for electron transfer for electrochemical sensors.^[107] We have been successful in using peptide nanostructures (PNS) as the dielectric layer both in top-gate and bottom-gate pentacene field-effect transistors (FETs).^[8,108] The nanostructures of PNS are obtained by a solid-vapor phase. **Figure 23** shows a schematic of a pentacene FET with SEM images of the pentacene-PNS (top left) and only PNS film (top right) fabricated in our laboratory. Highly concentrated peptide films yield microstructures, and upon evaporation of pentacene (which is the active organic semiconductor layer), a further promotion of a nanostructuring effect is observed. Using the standard saturation regime FET I-V characteristics [$\mu_{FET} = 2L/WC_0(\partial\sqrt{I_{ds}}/\partial V_g)^2$, where C_0 is the effective capacitance, W the channel width, L the channel length of the transistor, V_g and I_{ds} are the gate voltage and source-drain current, respectively], the charge carrier mobility is extracted. The p-type charge carrier

mobilities were $\sim 10^{-2}$ - 10^{-3} cm²/Vs. As a comparison, FF peptide (without any nanostructures) was also used as a dielectric film in pentacene FETs; there was a complete break down under bias-stress (in less than 30 min) indicating that the nano/micro-structuring of the peptides is crucial for stability of FETs. A novel feature of the PNS dielectric is that it allows for an easy fabrication route towards top-gate FET architectures, which could have a potential application in biosensing.

Figure 23. Schematic of a PNS-based pentacene FET. The top left shows a SEM image of pentacene-PNS and the right image is only from a PNS layer. The transistor output and transfer characteristics of the device are shown on the right panel. Reprinted with permission from [8] Copyright 2019, American Chemical Society.

In an equally transformative fashion, we have demonstrated the functionalization of self-assembled peptide nanostructures with blue-emitting conjugated polymers, opening up a new generation of biodegradable materials in organic electronics.^[109,110] In particular, FF nanostructures were functionalized by two side chain substituted polyfluorenes (PF) – di-octyl substituted PF (PF8) and ethyl-hexyl substituted PF (PF2/6). PF8 with its long di-octyl side chains shows a better binding affinity towards FF nanostructures compared to PF2/6. Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations show a higher van der Waals interaction energy for FF:PF8 compared with FF:PF2/6, corroborating the optical spectroscopy and electron microscopy results, as shown in Figure 24. The FF:PF nanocomposites were further utilized in light-emitting diodes (LEDs). The electroluminescence (EL) from these structures was comparable to the pristine PF8 LEDs (Figure 24-d)). Biodegradability tests from FF:PF8 nanocomposite films show more than 80% weight loss in two hours by enzymatic action compared to PF8 pristine films, which do not degrade. Self-assembly of FF nanostructures with organic semiconductors, thus, opens up a new generation of biocompatible and biodegradable materials in organic electronics.

Figure 24. (a) Schematic of monomers of PF2/6 and PF8 being attached to a FF nanotube. (b) MD simulations showing panoramic view of the distribution of PF8 monomers on nanotube surface. (c) TEM image of FF:PF8. (d) EL spectra from pristine PF8 and FF:PF8 LEDs. Reprinted with permission from ^[110] Copyright 2019, John Wiley and Sons.

4.5. Antimicrobial agents

Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) are naturally found in all living organisms, and they are considered the first line of defense of the innate immune system. The advancement of proteomic and genomic techniques allowed the identification of more than 2000 sequences of natural AMPs over the last 20 years.^[111, 112]

The increased interest in this type of peptides is directly related to the appearance of microorganisms multi- or super-resistant to available antibiotics. In addition to direct antimicrobial activity, AMPs carry immunomodulatory properties, which make them especially interesting compounds for the development of novel therapeutics.^[111-113]

The fundamental structure of AMPs consists of 10–100 amino acids; this structure displays an overall positive charge that ranges from +2 to +11,^[113] and it contains a substantial proportion of hydrophobic and cationic amino acid residues that make the molecule able to adopt an amphipathic design. In section 1 it was described how the auto-organization of peptides occur. In the case of the AMPs, they most belong to the first two categories (*Figure 2*). In the case of the α -helical peptides, they are often unstructured in aqueous solutions, but they adopt an amphipathic helical structure when they come in contact with a biological membrane.^[111, 114]

Most AMPs have the same mechanism of action, which consists of damaging the physical integrity of the microbial membrane and/or translocating through the membrane into the cytoplasm of the bacteria to act on the intracellular targets, which causes the inhibition of

DNA/RNA/protein synthesis, as shown in Figure 20-A.^[115] This mechanism is only possible because unlike the eukaryotic cell membranes where the lipid layer is turned into the cell, the bacterial lipid layer is facing the outer side, and the negatively charged phospholipids are on the membrane surface. Since the AMPs are cationic, they can interact with the target membranes by both electrostatic forces and hydrophobic effects (Figure 20-B).^[116] Because of the high affinity between the AMPs and membranes, the development of a resistance mechanism to these compounds is extremely unlikely, even in the face of high genetic variability and mutagenic capacity of microorganisms.

Selectivity of Antimicrobial peptides

Figure 25. A) Action mechanism and selectivity of AMPs; B) Selectivity of antimicrobial peptides. Reprinted with permission from ^[117] Copyright 2019, American Chemical Society.

Despite all the advantages that natural AMPs may present, there are still several challenges that need to be overcome to broaden their therapeutic applications. These challenges include the toxicity of AMPs, the susceptibility of peptides to proteolytic degradation in vivo, their pharmaceutical and pharmacological limitations (increased stability, reduced clearance rates), and the cost of their production. Even so, the few AMP candidates that reached the market are mostly naturally occurring cyclic peptides. These AMPs are normally produced by microbiological approaches, which require purification and isolation steps.^[111, 118]

One of the ways of improving the clinical performance of AMPs, in addition to the synthesis of non-natural mimic peptides, lies in the conjugation of the sequences of interest to polymers or nanoparticles (see section 2.5). This kind of hybrid peptides have shown interesting results because they present a natural antimicrobial activity, and the synthesis of this type of composite is widely described in the literature (Figure 25).^[117]

Figure 26. Schematic diagram for the synthesis of AMP-SH conjugated AuNPs. Route A: fully deprotected peptide. Route B: side-chain-protected peptide. Reprinted with permission from ^[117] Copyright 2019, American Chemical Society.

In 2017, Casciaro et al. demonstrated microbicidal activity against a multidrug-resistant *P. aeruginosa* strain of AuNP-conjugated esculentin-1a (Esc1-21), a low solubility AMP. The conjugation between the NPs and the AMP led to a significant increase in solubility with respect to the isolated peptide; however, it also diminished the enzymatic action on Esc1-21 and prolonged its time of action. AuNPs @ Esc1-21 presented higher cytotoxic activity compared with that of free peptides, and it also had a faster action and a lower MBC50. This study also demonstrated that the conjugate has as a mechanism of action that disrupts the bacterial membrane (Figure 22).^[119]

Figure 27. (A) Schematic diagram of stepwise synthesis of AMP–NH₂ conjugated Au–NPs. (B) Esculentin-1a (1-21)–NH₂-coated Au–NPs and a TEM micrograph of its interaction with *P. aeruginosa*. (C) TEM micrographs of *P. aeruginosa* cells after 15 min treatment with (A, left) AuNPs @ Esc(1-21) or (B, right) buffer. Adapted with permission from ^[117] Copyright 2019, American Chemical Society.

4.6. Application in catalysis

As discussed earlier, peptide sequences can be used as catalysts in organic reactions. The choice of the amino acids present in the peptide favours the increase in its functionality and the creation of different polymorphs, which promotes a more selective catalysis.^[120, 121]

In recent years, the use of amino acids and peptides in asymmetric catalysis has been a research topic worldwide, from both the synthetic and mechanistic points of view.^[122-124] Proline amino acids and proline motif structures are the most widely used organocatalysts in aldol reactions,^[125,126] but there are few works showing the effect of aggregation or supramolecular arrangement on the catalytic activity in these systems. The use of peptide self-assembly opens up new opportunities for catalyst design that are not found in natural enzymes. This allows the formation of more effective contacts by the functional groups and the development of specific conformations.

Recently, Escuder *et al.*^[127] presented a structural and catalytic study of different polymorphic forms that were found in clusters and hydrogels of compound **7** using different

preparation conditions (i.e., heating temperature, heating time, maturation period, pH variations, and ultrasound treatment time). These preparation changes allowed the formation of four major polymorphs and four minor polymorphs. Three major polymorphs (A, B, and D) were characterized by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), potentiometric titration, wide-angle X-ray diffraction (WAXD), circular dichroism, infrared, transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) (Figure 28).

Figure 28. TEM images (upper panels) and FESEM images (lower panels) of polymorphic aggregates A (A, B), B (C, D) and D (E, F). Reprinted with permission from ^[127] Copyright 2019, Royal Society of Chemistry.

Subsequently, polymorphs A, B, and D were used as catalysts in the aldol reaction between cyclohexanone and p-nitrobenzaldehyde. Yields higher than 95% were obtained, and the levels of diastereo- and enantioselectivity were satisfactory. However, different reaction rates were found for each material, as shown in Figure 29.

Conditions of polymorph preparation

Polymorph	A	B	D
Concentration (mM)	2	2	2 (pH 7)
Heating temperature (°C)	100	100	-
Heating time (h)	2	16	-
Aging time (min)	-	10	10
Ultrasounds time (h)	2	-	-

Figure 29. Yields obtained for aldol reactions vs. reaction time. Reprinted with permission from ^[128] Copyright 2019, Royal Society of Chemistry.

According to these authors, two factors may explain the findings. Each factor involves a different proposal with respect to the catalytic site. I) Catalysis occurs in solution: differences in the solubility of polymorphs in water lead to different concentrations of available catalytic sites. II) Catalysis occurs on the surface fibers: differences in the molecular aggregates of polymorphs lead to differences in the accessibility of catalytic sites.

More recently, we have developed a study where the self-assembly of a *L*-proline-containing lipopeptide PRW-C₁₆ (P: *L*-proline, R: *L*-arginine, W: *L*-tryptophan) was explored for promoting aldol reactions in excess water.^[129] Then, the catalytic activity of the lipopeptide for the direct asymmetric aldol reaction was investigated by performing a model reaction using *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde and cyclohexanone at room temperature, in the presence and absence of water. The lipopeptide showed better catalytic efficiency in aqueous media, by comparison with its performance in organic media (neat cyclohexanone), since the micelle seems to provide an environment that enhances catalysis. Therefore, the lipopeptide structures were successfully applied as a supramolecular catalytic system for direct aldol reactions in excess water. Our results show, for the first time, the viability of *L*-proline amphiphilic derivative micelles as a catalyst with excellent conversion and stereoselectivity. In contrast, poor results were obtained in the absence of the lipopeptide assemblies. The excellent results provided by the self-assembled structures demonstrate the potential of lipopeptide assemblies to catalyze aldol reactions in an environmentally friendly aqueous medium.

Hybrid peptides containing metallic nanoparticles (NPs) have also attracted great attention as catalysts.^[130-133] The metal-to-peptide molar concentration ratio influences the size and polymorphism of the conjugate hybrids in the aggregation process due to the availability of the surface area of the nanoparticles; this promotes different reaction kinetics.^[134,135] Moreover, the interactions within the chiral self-assembled peptides, which are in high proximity to the catalytically active Au ions, lead to better packing of chiral molecules that favour specific orientation of the reactants. These interactions result, for example, in the enhancement in the diastereoselectivity and enantioselectivity values of products.^[136,137]

5. Summary and prospects

In this review, we discussed the self-assembly properties of peptide nanomaterials in relationship with their design (amphiphilic peptides, ionic-complementary peptides, cyclic peptides) and composition (alkyl- and polymer conjugated peptides, hybrid peptides). We also showed how the morphology of peptide nanostructures can be influenced by environmental conditions, and how this dependence can be suitably exploited for the design of stimuli-

responsive systems. In the final section, we reviewed the applications of self-assembled peptide nanostructures, focussing on the biomedical (drug delivery, tissue engineering) and bionanotechnological (biosensing, catalysis) areas.

The great chemical diversity and versatility of the presented peptide systems open a wide field for the research and pave the way for technological development. The interactions between peptide groups and other compounds, whether biological or not, represent a vast area of scientific development to be explored. Given this scenario, it is evident how necessary is the in-depth understanding of the structural and dynamical factors controlling the formation of peptide nanostructures at the different levels of hierarchical self-assembly.

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